

THE IMPACT OF THE PANDEMIC ON THE CONSUMPTION OF NUTRITIONAL SUPPLEMENTS

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Abstract

Purpose – *The pandemic has influenced and brought major changes in the medical/nutritional system.*

Methodology/approach – *Documentary study on nutritional supplement consumption before and during the pandemic, case study on dietary supplement consumption during the pandemic, case study at a company distributing dietary supplements.*

Findings – *The paper is focused on economic and managerial analysis during the pandemic period, and the dietary supplement industry and distribution has shown rapid adaptation to the new conditions offered by the pandemic.*

Research limitations/implications – *The pandemic period produced changes that were also reflected in the behaviour of consumers of dietary supplements.*

Practical implications – *The paper provides a centralised picture of the trend in dietary supplement consumption during the pandemic period.*

Originality/value – *The paper identifies the trend of nutritional supplement consumption during the pandemic period.*

Key words: *nutritional supplements, determinants in the classification of nutritional supplements, distribution and marketing of nutritional supplements, customer behaviour during the pandemic period.*

Introduction

Socrates argued "there is one good, knowledge, and one evil, ignorance". (Phyllis, A. Balch, 2020) These words would do well to accompany us in all our actions, especially in relation to our health. So many of us lack information about how to maintain or improve our health. It would be good to be aware that nature has given us an inner healing force (the immune system) and natural substances suitable for the proper functioning of the human body; but unfortunately, there is the possibility of nutritional imbalances that can lead to health problems.

The foods we eat contain nutrients made up of vitamins, minerals, enzymes, amino acids, carbohydrates and fats. It is these nutrients that sustain life, providing us with the basic building blocks our bodies need to perform their daily functions for health. Nutrients are involved in all body processes, from fighting infection, to tissue repair, to thinking. Although nutrients have different functions, the common point is to keep the human body functioning well. A deficiency of these nutrients will cause malfunctioning of some organs or body systems. In order to prevent this, we need a proper diet and appropriate nutritional supplements.

The foundation of good health is a balanced and quality diet supported by supplements. Nutritional supplements are those food products that are used to supplement people's daily diet, they are those concentrated sources of nutrients or other substances with a nutritional effect, which can be marketed separately or in combination.

Nutritional supplements are intended solely for the purpose of having positive effects on various functions of the body for prophylactic purposes. They contain one or more characteristic substances

also called nutrients or active ingredients or substances, which could be vitamins, minerals, amino acids, enzymes, plant extracts.

Nutritional supplements can be classified according to their composition or the functions they perform:

1. Nutritional supplements can be classified on the basis of the essential nutrients contained in: micronutrients (vitamins, minerals), macronutrients (amino acids, proteins, lipids, fibre), phytonutrients (phytochemicals from plants) and combinations of these listed nutrients.
2. Nutritional supplements can be classified on the basis of their therapeutic areas of action into dietary supplements with antioxidant power, anti-ageing, arthritis, rheumatism, cardio-vascular system, diabetes, deworming, dermatological disorders, detoxification, endocrinology, gastrointestinal system, genitourinary system, hydration, immune system, renal system, nervous system, nutrition, osteoporosis, ophthalmology, metabolic regulation and weight control, sports nutrition and muscle tissue rebuilding, skin, hair and nail care.
3. Nutritional supplements can be classified based on consumer/user groups into nutritional supplements for: adults, men, women (pregnant or breastfeeding women, menopausal women), children, adolescents, sports, vegans or vegetarians, people with disabilities. (Phyllis, A. Balch, 2020)

Nutritional supplements can be marketed through the following institutions: pharmacies, drugstores, drugstores and warehouses of supplement manufacturers and importers. Their purchase can be made by direct, physical purchase from these institutions or through the online environment, when the purchase is made using the websites of these institutions.

Consumers, primary care providers, health insurers and employers increasingly recognise the value of preventive health and wellness. Nutritional supplements are cost-effective in supporting overall health and well-being of the human body.

Between 2019 and 2021, the overall DSX score increased nationally in every category, but growth was led by supplements for sleep, immunity, and brain health. During the global pandemic, consumers initially focused on immunity to help themselves stay healthy during COVID-19. But as more options emerged in 2021, consumer interest shifted to brain and sleep supplements to manage stress from the pandemic, while immunity supplements declined slightly. Those most affected by these were active adults, especially those in urban areas. (“Dietary Supplements Index | Consumer Healthcare Products Association”)

Annual consumer surveys show that the use of nutritional supplements is more prevalent in the United States when occasional and seasonal use are considered in addition to regular use. Most nutritional supplement users consume a multivitamin, but there are many who take a combination of products. The main reasons given for using supplements are for general health and well-being of the body or to fill nutrient gaps. Nutritional supplement users are more likely to adopt a variety of healthy habits, indicating that supplement use is part of an overall approach to healthy living. (“Consumer Usage and Reasons for Using Dietary Supplements: Report of a Series of Surveys - PubMed”)

The US has emerged as a top market for nutritional supplements due to consumer affordability and dominated this market, accounting for the largest revenue share of 34.8% in 2021. The global nutritional supplements market size was valued at USD 151.9 billion in 2021 and is expected to expand at a CAGR of 8.9% from 2022 to 2030.

Vitamins, minerals and immune-boosting herbs witnessed an increase in demand in 2020. Vitamin as an ingredient dominated the nutritional supplement market and accounted for more than 30.8% of revenue share in 2021, due to high demand from active professionals and athletes for energy management.

Tablets segment led the nutritional supplements market and accounted for 33.6% of revenue share in 2021. Higher prevalence of multivitamin products in tablet form due to easy dosing, ease of administration, low cost, longer shelf life is expected to ensure a positive impact.

The adult segment dominated the market and accounted for the highest revenue share of 46.6% in 2021. Changing lifestyles and hectic work schedules among active adults lead to nutritional deficiencies which are expected to lead to increased consumption of nutritional supplements.

Increasing number of geriatric populations in regions such as North America, Europe, and Asia Pacific is expected to augment the market growth over the forecast period. As geriatric population is susceptible to more infections, the demand for immune support from these pandemic users is expected to grow at a higher rate.

The offline segment dominated the market and accounted for the highest revenue share of 81.0% in 2021. The offline subcategories include supermarket/hypermarkets, pharmacies, convenience stores, specialty stores. Supermarkets/hypermarkets contribute significantly to the sales of dietary supplements in Europe and North America due to higher prevalence. In the offline segment, supermarkets and hypermarkets accounted for 33.9% of total dietary supplement sales in 2021.

Sales of nutritional supplements through online distribution channels are expected to register the highest growth in the coming years. People's fast-paced lifestyles, increased number of internet users, easy access to a range of brands, 24/7 product availability, convenience of shopping and a wide range of products on offer are factors driving sales of nutritional supplements through online distribution channels. Sales of nutritional supplements through online distribution channels are expected to register the highest growth in the coming years. The spread of COVID-19 has attracted many customers to e-commerce platforms, leading to easy availability of different brands of supplements to consumers. ("Dietary Supplements Market Size Report, 2022-2030")

North America is expected to be the largest market during the forecast period. This is attributed to the widespread consumption of nutritional supplements in the US and Canada. The Asia-Pacific nutritional supplements market is expected to register the highest growth over the forecast period. This is attributed to the rising popularity of functional and fortified foods in the region. The global market is growing rapidly in South Asian countries such as Vietnam due to the increased consumption of multivitamins and minerals. The growing geriatric population in the region is also a major factor driving market growth. ("Dietary Supplements Market Share, Size, Forecast:2026 | MarketsandMarkets")

Research methodology used in this paper

The survey of the statistical study was carried out on a group of 270 people from 18 counties of Romania, more precisely the interviewees are from Brasov, Galati, Braila, Mures, Sibiu, Covasna, Harghita, Bucharest, Ilfov, Dolj, Timis, Cluj, Prahova, Buzau, Iasi, Vaslui, Neamt, Suceava counties.

The objective of this survey was to discover the impact of the pandemic on the consumption of nutritional supplements for the population in our country, as well as to raise awareness of the contribution of dietary supplements to maintain health.

The number of items in the questionnaire is 10. The data collection and processing was carried out using Google Forms software for the whole group.

Interpretation of results

Regarding question 1: Did you consume nutritional supplements before the pandemic?

62.1% answered positively and 37.9% answered negatively.

On question 2: Did you consume more nutritional supplements during the pandemic?

57.8% answered positively and 42.2% answered negatively

On question 3: Do you currently consume more nutritional supplements than you did during the pandemic?

22.4% answered positively and 77.6% answered negatively.

On question 4: Have you used nutritional supplements for a specific condition?

47.6% answered positively and 52.4% answered negatively.

On question 5: Did you use nutritional supplements to improve the functioning of your immune system during the pandemic?

68.4% answered positively and 31.6% answered negatively.

On question 6: Did the pandemic make you more concerned about improving your health?

66.3% answered positively and 33.7% answered negatively

On question 7: Are you willing to continue taking food supplements?

71.3% answered positively and 28.7% answered negatively

On question 8: Do you document nutritional supplements through specialist advisors/doctors/pharmacists?

59.9% answered positively and 40.1% answered negatively

Concerning question 9: Do you inform yourself about nutritional supplements from information/promotional/internet material?

70.4% answered positively and 29.6% answered negatively

Concerning question 10: You do not do any research.

24.5% answered positively and 75.5% answered negatively.

Conclusions: It appears that before the pandemic there was a significant consumption of nutritional supplements (62.1%), but during the pandemic the consumption of nutritional supplements increased (57.8%), and people are still consuming dietary supplements because the pandemic has not ended, and others are consuming even more nutritional supplements at this time (22.4%).

Consumers of nutritional supplements also use them for preventive purposes (52.4%), but mainly for the proper functioning of the immune system (68.4%), and the pandemic has made them aware of the importance of health (66.3%) and people are willing to continue consuming nutritional supplements (71.3%).

A significant proportion seek expert advice on nutritional supplements (59.9%), and thanks to the information age we are in, a large percentage also research themselves (70.4%), but not least it is encouraging that a very high percentage of people are willing to continue to learn about nutritional supplements (75.5%).

In conclusion, the consumption of nutritional supplements has increased during the pandemic period and people want to continue consuming nutritional supplements because they are aware of the importance of prevention and are eager to accumulate new information about nutritional supplements.

The case study on the possible changes perceived by a consultant in the consumption of supplements was carried out at the company CC specializing in such products, which started its activity in 1998 in Canada, and for over 20 years, has been helping people around the world to improve their lifestyle with the help of unique products of very high quality.

The company has sales offices in 39 countries, distributing in 189 countries, the company's portfolio contains more than 200 health and beauty products, and production is carried out in 10 countries worldwide. These factories use innovative technologies in the production process, raw materials from natural sources, resulting in products in a balanced and bioavailable form. The company's main priorities are product quality, safety and attractiveness, quickly bringing to market innovative solutions to support health and beauty. ("Despre Companie")

The company's communication with customers has been carried out through the company's advisors who support customers with information and details about the products, but during the pandemic period the communication strategy has expanded to the online environment: webinars, presentations, seminars, conferences, inviting specialists in the medical/nutritional field who have held educational webinars on general information about a healthy lifestyle.

The study in CC was conducted on a company advisor in the ante, pandemic and present period. Quantification of sales was done in points, which represent the value of sales in lei, each product being assigned a certain number of points according to its value in lei.

Before the start of the pandemic, in January 2020 I had a turnover of sales representing 1750 points, when the pandemic started in March I had a turnover of 2500 points, and these sales increased in May 2020 to 4000 points, so that in October 2020 I had a turnover of 6500 points which at the end of the pandemic year 2020 in December became 8000 points. Summing up, in 2020 the turnover increased 4.5 times and we had 120 new people consuming dietary supplements in 2020.

The year 2021 continued its upward trend in this nutritional supplements market both in terms of turnover and in terms of new people joining who consumed monthly supplements. In the months of March and April 2021 we had the highest turnover of 15,500 points, and in the other months of 2021 the turnover averaged 10,000 points, and the number of new people who became regular consumers of nutritional supplements increased by 161 people in 2021.

In 2022 the volume turnover of sulphiment remained at 12,000 points, with only a slight increase, and the number of new consumers increased by 26 people until June.

It emerges that the highest receptivity of the population to the nutritional supplements segment was in the peak pandemic period, i.e. March 2019 - December 2021 when the volume of sales increased, but also the number of new consumers.

Final conclusions: the SARS COV19 pandemic has impacted various areas of business globally, but more importantly has brought major changes to the healthcare/nutrition system.

From the two studies, statistical and case studies, it appears that during the pandemic the consumption of nutritional supplements increased and the population paid more attention to the well-being of the body, focusing on prevention and health improvement. This has been achieved by taking necessary and beneficial nutritional supplements to support the immune system, manage stress, remove fatigue and restore the circadian rhythm in order to gain energy and overall well-being.

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